

THE ROLE OF LEXIS IN THE LEARNING AND UNDERSTANDING THE LANGUAGE

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Abstract: By categorizing vocabulary into meaningful groups, teachers can offer students structured chances to explore and learn new words. These categories act as cognitive support, helping learners gain a deeper understanding of word usage and relationships in the language.

Key words: semantic, transportation, frequency, context, word family, suffix.

Lexis, or vocabulary, is grouped in various ways to facilitate learning and understanding. These groupings help learners organize and categorize words based on their meaning, usage, and relationship to one another. Here are some common ways lexis is grouped:

1. Semantic Categories: Lexis can be grouped according to shared meanings or semantic fields. For example, words related to animals, food, emotions, or transportation can be organized into separate categories. This approach helps learners associate related words and understand their connections within a specific context.

2. Word Families: Words that share a common root or base can be grouped into word families. By examining prefixes, suffixes, and root words, learners can identify patterns and relationships among words. For instance, words like "happy," "happiness," and "unhappy" belong to the same word family based on the root word "happy."

3. Frequency Bands: Lexis can be grouped based on frequency of use in language. High-frequency words, commonly known as sight words or core vocabulary, are essential for basic communication and understanding. Lower-

frequency words, often specific to certain domains or contexts, are less commonly used but are still important for developing a richer vocabulary.

4. Register and Style: Lexis can vary depending on the formality or informality of language use. Words may be grouped according to different registers, such as formal, informal, technical, or colloquial language. Additionally, words may be categorized based on their stylistic features, such as literary, poetic, or slang expressions.

5. Word Formation: Lexis can also be grouped based on how words are formed. This includes compound words (e.g., "blackboard"), derivations (e.g., "happiness" from "happy"), and inflections (e.g., verb conjugations like "walk," "walked," "walking"). Understanding word formation processes helps learners recognize and generate new vocabulary.

By organizing lexis into meaningful groups, educators can provide learners with structured opportunities to explore and acquire vocabulary. These groupings serve as cognitive scaffolding, guiding learners toward a deeper understanding of how words are used and related in language.

Techniques for recycling vocabulary

Recycling vocabulary is essential for reinforcing learning and promoting long-term retention. Here are several techniques for effectively recycling vocabulary:

1. Flashcards: Utilize flashcards as a versatile tool for vocabulary recycling. Learners can create their own flashcards or use digital flashcard apps to review and practice vocabulary on a regular basis. Incorporate activities like matching games, quizzes, or spaced repetition techniques to reinforce learning.

2. Contextualized Practice: Provide opportunities for learners to use vocabulary in meaningful contexts through speaking, writing, and listening activities. Incorporate role-plays, discussions, storytelling, and writing prompts that require the use of target vocabulary in authentic communication situations.

3. Vocabulary Games: Engage learners in interactive and enjoyable vocabulary games to make recycling more engaging and memorable. Games like bingo,

charades, Pictionary, word scrambles, and vocabulary jeopardy can help reinforce vocabulary in a fun and interactive way.

4. Word of the Day/Week: Introduce a new word of the day or week and encourage learners to incorporate it into their daily communication. Provide opportunities for learners to explore the meaning, usage, and context of the word through discussions, examples, and activities.

5. Vocabulary Challenges: Organize vocabulary challenges or competitions where learners compete to demonstrate their knowledge and mastery of vocabulary. This could include spelling bees, vocabulary quizzes, or scavenger hunts that require learners to find and use specific vocabulary items.

6. Integrated Skills Activities: Design activities that integrate vocabulary practice with other language skills, such as reading comprehension, listening comprehension, and writing tasks. This allows learners to reinforce vocabulary learning while developing overall language proficiency.

By incorporating these techniques into instruction, educators can create a dynamic and engaging learning environment that promotes the effective recycling of vocabulary, leading to improved retention and mastery of language skills over time.

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